

Autonomous Control Operations for Energy-Efficient Packet Optical Networks

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ABSTRACT

Recent efforts have focused on integrating packet and optical technologies to meet growing broadband demands while enhancing cost and energy efficiency. Within this framework, strategies are oriented towards adopting coherent DWDM small form factor transceivers (*pluggables*) with the aim of simplifying IPoWDM networks. This study specifically examines two IPoWDM network scenarios. The first scenario involves the use of traditional external transponders situated between routers and the optical line system. In the second scenario, transponders are eliminated, and routers' ports are equipped with transceiver *pluggables* directly connected to ROADMs. The power consumption of the involved network elements for each scenario are detailed. Additionally, we explore the autonomous operations managed by a SDN controller when dynamically provisioning connectivity services targeting the reduction of the network power consumption. To this end, an SDN controller architecture is presented offloading the computationally intensive routing function to an externalized server. The workflow, functions, and APIs used by the SDN controller are detailed. Particularly, it is presented potential extensions to the ONF TAPI Context for describing transceiver power-consumptions attributes required when dynamically executing energy-aware path computations.

Keywords: IP over WDM networks, Energy Efficiency, Pluggable Transceivers, Software Defined Networking

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of packet and optical transport technologies has been intensively explored in the last years to cope with the growth of broadband services while simultaneously enhancing efficiency in terms of CAPEX, OPEX, and power consumption [1]-[3]. In this context, the emergence of coherent DWDM small form factor transceivers (*pluggables*) such as the 400/800 ZR+ is seen strategic where router ports are equipped with such devices and directly connected to ROADMs. This does simplify IPoWDM networks removing typical "grey" interfaces to external DWDM multi-rate transponders (100 – 400 Gb/s) [3]. By adopting this, metro and core network infrastructures can more effectively accommodate the growing demand for transport capacity, simultaneously progressing towards greater sustainability from both economic and energy perspectives.

The SDN controller handles the autonomous control and configuration of both packet and optical devices, leveraging well-defined APIs like OpenConfig and OpenROADM. Thus, packet connectivity services are autonomously created, updated, and terminated. In general, packet services determine their ingress and egress routers along with specific requirements such as guaranteed bandwidth and maximum permitted latency. Upon a packet service demand, the SDN controller undertakes the path computation function to find the route (i.e., nodes and links) and select the network resources and their configuration attributes (i.e., router transceivers *operational models*, optical frequency slots, etc.) fulfilling the service demands. Within the energy efficiency framework, the path computation must aim not only accomplishing optimal network resource utilization but also reduced/conserved network power consumption. To do that, the SDN controller offloads the path computation to a dedicated and specialized path computation server. This can host multi-objective routing algorithms based on either *heuristics* or advanced Machine Learning (ML) trained approaches. In both strategies, they require as input the network status information composed by the SDN controller. This is referred to as *Context* and describes the packet/optical topology (i.e., nodes and links), the available link's optical spectrum, the transceivers capabilities, as well as the power consumption parameters (in Watts) when a device such as DWDM transceivers/transponders, routers, ROADMs, etc. are *activated/powered-up*.

We overview two IPoWDM network scenarios, both considering ZR+ coherent *pluggables*. The former is based on traditional external *muxponder-transponder* (Xponder) placed between routers and ROADMs; the second considers DWDM pluggable transceivers in router ports connected to the ROADMs. For both approaches, it is discussed the power consumption of the packet and optical network elements. Next, we delve into the autonomous control operations handled by the SDN controller where routing computation is done in a dedicated server. We detail the interactions between the SDN controller and Path Computation Server, facilitated through the ONF T-API framework. Additionally, we examine TAPI Context extensions as transceiver profiles to provide power consumption attributes used to perform network energy efficiency path computations.

2. Packet - Optical Transport Networks: Architectures

Fig. 1(a) depicts traditional integration of router and optical ROADMs via an Xponder (external DWDM transponder). Specifically, routers ports are equipped with short-reach “grey” interfaces (e.g., at 100 Gb/s) physically attached to a multi-rate DWDM Xponder. The Xponder allows electrical-optical conversions offering the capabilities to i) *groom* lower-rate 100Gb/s packet flows into higher data rate (e.g., 300 to 800 Gb/s) thanks to the adjustment of modulation formats (DP-QPSK, DP-8QAM, DP-16QAM) and symbol-rates (e.g., 40 or 60 Gbaud); and ii) to regenerate the optical signals when needed without the router utilization [2]. In general, Xponders provides longer optical path reach improving the spectral efficiency, whilst increasing the power consumption. On the other hand, Fig. 1(b) illustrates the IPoWDM scenario where DWDM pluggable transceivers are placed into the routers’ ports and then connected to the optical line system (ROADMs). Therefore, neither grey interfaces are plugged into the routers nor external DWDM transceivers are required. The packet and optical infrastructure are simplified which may lead to enhance CAPEX [1], space and power footprint [1][3]. However, as discussed in [2], the lower reach of optical channels when compared to IPoWDM with Xponders brings notable implications such as the need to perform electrical regenerations at intermediate routers [2]. Consequently, routers with DWDM *pluggables* could be used more often, worsening the spectral efficiency and, to some extent, increasing the power consumption, latency, and cost.

Figure 1. Packet-Optical integrated architecture: a) Xponder; b) DWDM pluggable transceivers.

The configuration for both IPoWDM networks is steered by a centralized SDN controller which, leveraging the disaggregation concept, uses standardized APIs with well-defined data models such as openConfig and openROADM. Through these APIs, the controller communicates with the devices’ SDN agents governing routers’ *pluggables*, Xponders, and ROADMs. The agents are integrated into the operating systems of the network elements and perform *mappings/translation* functions of the SDN controller commands (e.g., selecting the central frequency, operational mode in a pluggable, etc.) to the specific data plane interface drivers as well as hardware abstraction or telemetry data understood/consumed by the SDN controller operations.

3. Overview of the Packet- Optical Network Power Consumption

A commonly employed energy efficiency metric evaluates the ratio between the average network throughput (in Tb/s) and the average network power consumption (in kW). Indeed, a higher ratio indicates a more energy-efficient network. When deploying a new connectivity service, it is calculated the increase in power consumption once the service is operational. This corresponds to the activation of unused (*slept down*) network elements such as transceiver *pluggables*, ROADMs, etc. In the considered IPoWDM architectures, power consumption is influenced by several factors: 1) the *idle* power usage, encompassing components such as power suppliers, fans, DSPs, etc. of the Xponders, routers, cards, grey/DWDM ZR+ *pluggables*, which collectively represent 95% of the total power consumption; 2) the programmed transceiver operational modes (e.g., symbol rate, modulation format); 3) the activated ROADMs and optical line amplifiers.

Table I outlines the power consumption for each network element forming an optical connection deployed on each of the considered IPoWDM architectures. By doing so, the SDN controller can estimate the increase in the power consumption based on the computed path. For example, depending on the selected operational modes (1 to 4) tied to different modulation formats (e.g., DP-QPSK, -8QAM, and -16QAM) and symbol rate, ZR+ transceivers achieve different optical signal reach resulting in diverse power consumptions.

Table 1. Assumed power consumption for the packet and optical devices and elements.

		Operational Mode	Modulation Format	Symbol [Gbd] & Bit Rates[b/s]	Power [W]	Distance [km]
Packet Devices	DWDM transceiver ZR+	1	DP-QPSK	30 / 100	12	3000
		2	DP-QPSK	60 / 200	15	1500
		3	DP-8QAM	60 / 300	19	1000
		4	DP-16QAM	60 / 400	22	700
Packet Devices	Router	Description			Power [W]	
		Environmental idle power consumption (P_{idle}) of an activated router, including power supplies, switching fabric, fans.			385	
		Data power consumption (P_{data}) for the equipped router port (e.g., at 100Gb/s) and plugged grey transceivers (at 100Gb/s)			Router port @ 100Gb/s: 40 Grey transceiver @ 100Gb/s: 3.5	
Optical System Elements	Xponder	Description			Power [W]	
		xPonder supporting client 4 x 100 Gb/s flows and 1-line DWDM 400 Gb/s transceiver			(with activated 4 client lines and 1 DWDM line transceiver) ~250	
	ROADM	Description			Power [W]	
		Idle power of an active ROADM. It includes the dissipated power of fans, control system, optical backplane, etc.			150	
Optical System Elements	ROADM	P_{OLP} accounts for the power consumption of an active optical line degree: WSSes, (pre-and booster) optical amplifiers			85	
		Description			Power [W]	
Optical System Elements	Optical Line Amplifiers	P_{OLA} determines the power consumption of an activated (in use) optical line amplifier (regardless of the optical flows)			12	

4. Autonomous SDN-based Control Operations

The SDN controller handles the lifecycle management of the connectivity services. Upon receiving a request (e.g., via a NorthBound Interface) from a User, the controller coordinates for: i) computing the path and resources that fulfils the connection requirements (i.e., bandwidth, maximum latency); ii) managing the configuration of the selected packet and optical transport network elements.

Figure 2. (a) SDN Controller workflow; (b) TAPI Context Profile extensions to support power-consumption transceiver capabilities; (c) TAPI Context node w/ NEP's profiles.

Fig. 2 a) depicts the workflow conducted by the SDN controller to automatically process incoming connectivity service requests. The NBI, based on the ONF T-API and built upon RESTCONF protocol and YANG models, is exposed by the SDN controller to allow an external entity requesting the provisioning of a Digital Signal Rate (DSR) service. Then, the SDN controller initiates the path computation and resource selection in both packet and optical network elements. This process can be computationally intensive. Thus, the path computation function is externalized to a dedicated ML-assisted Path Computation Server to execute the

routing algorithm. The output is formed by a spatial path (i.e., nodes and links) and resources meeting the service demands and constraints. In the IPoWDM context, the routing algorithms relies on the so-called Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA). The input of the RSA algorithms comprises not only the connection requirements but also the *Context*. This context provides the network topology formed by routers, ROADMs, links attributes (e.g., distance), available optical spectrum, and transponder/*pluggables* capabilities (e.g., operational modes).

Prior to trigger the RSA algorithm, the Path Computation Server polls the SDN controller to retrieve the *Context* sending a RESTCONF GET method. As said, the TAPI *Context* contains the list of nodes specifying their Node Edge Points (NEPs) (see Fig. 2(c)). A pair of NEPs hosted in different nodes are inter-connected with a link. For each NEP, relevant attributes are detailed such as the available/occupied optical spectrum. For the energy-efficient path computation, the TAPI Context is extended to provide power consumption information for both pluggables and Xponders. To do that, we leverage the TAPI Context Profile concept [5]. Profiles provide static data information that can be referred by other TAPI object such as NEPs. We propose to augment the *transceiver profile* for each operational mode listed in Table 1. As shown in Fig. 2(b), for operational mode 1, the profile *dp-qpsk-30Gbd* is created which includes: the frequency range (i.e., upper, and lower frequencies) in Hz, the minimum and maximum powers for transmission and reception in Watts, the standard modulation format set to QPSK, the symbol rate in Gbaud, the power consumption in Watts, and the maximum supported distance in km. Similar profiles are built for the operational modes 2-4 specified in Table 1. Then, each router or Xponder NEP attached to a transceiver pluggable can be modelled by a list of transceiver profiles.

Once the TAPI Context information is retrieved by the Path Computation Element, the RSA algorithm is computed, and the output notified to the SDN controller. The successful path computation determines the nodes (routers and ROADMs), links, frequency slot to be allocated, and selected transceivers configuration.

4.1 Energy-Aware Routing Approaches

The energy-aware RSA (EA-RSA) algorithm can rely on either a heuristic strategy (e.g., modified *K-Shortest Path*) or exploiting an offline ML-based trained EA-RSA algorithm (e.g., Deep Reinforcement Learning). In the former, the EA-RSA algorithm upon the retrieved TAPI Context iterates over the different transceivers operational modes to find *K* candidate paths. For each k^{th} path, the output meets the service requirements, fulfils the spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints, and simultaneously reduced the network power consumption. This results in a complex multi-objective path computation where it is likely that optimizing one objective (e.g., network resource utilization to favour the throughput) leads to increase the overall power consumption and vice versa. Due to that, it is being recognized that the adoption of AI/ML trained models could substantially improve the decision-making for different network states and achieve a better trade-off between throughput and power consumption when compared to traditional heuristic approaches [4].

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work overviews two IPoWDM infrastructures upon the emergence of the pluggable transceivers: i) using traditional external Xponders; and ii) equipping routers' ports with programmable (modulation format and symbol rate) WDM ZR+ *pluggables*. More specifically, it is addressed the sustainability from the energy-efficiency perspective detailing the network power consumption of the devices involved in each IPoWDM strategy. Next, an SDN control architecture is discussed whose energy-aware path computation is delegated to a dedicated server. To do that, ONF TAPI Context extensions are proposed to augment transceiver profiles with power consumption parameters. This becomes essential to devise energy-aware routing algorithms (either heuristics or AI/ML trained models) to improve the trade-off between throughput and power consumption.

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